

Expelliarmus: Semantic-Centric Virtual Machine Image Management in IaaS Clouds

Nishant Saurabh^{a,b,*}, Shajulin Benedict^c, Jorge G. Barbosa^d and Radu Prodan^a

^aInstitute of Information Technology, University of Klagenfurt, Austria

^bInstitute of Computer Science, University of Innsbruck, Austria

^cIndian Institute of Information Technology, Kottayam, India

^dLIACC, Faculdade de Engenharia da Universidade do Porto, Portugal

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Virtual machine image management
Semantic similarity
Storage optimization
Virtual machine image publishing
Virtual machine image retrieval

ABSTRACT

Infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) Clouds concurrently accommodate diverse sets of user requests, requiring an efficient strategy for storing and retrieving virtual machine images (VMIs) at a large scale. The VMI storage management requires dealing with multiple VMIs, typically in the magnitude of gigabytes, which entails VMI sprawl issues hindering the elastic resource management and provisioning. Unfortunately, existing techniques to facilitate VMI management overlook VMI semantics (i.e. at the level of base image and software packages), with either restricted possibility to identify and extract reusable functionalities or with higher VMI publishing and retrieval overheads. In this paper, we propose Expelliarmus, a novel VMI management system that helps to minimize VMI storage, publishing and retrieval overheads. To achieve this goal, Expelliarmus incorporates three complementary features. First, it models VMIs as semantic graphs to facilitate their similarity computation. Second, it provides a semantically-aware VMI decomposition and base image selection to extract and store non-redundant base image and software packages. Third, it assembles VMIs based on the required software packages upon user request. We evaluate Expelliarmus through a representative set of synthetic Cloud VMIs on a real test-bed. Experimental results show that our semantic-centric approach is able to optimize the repository size by 2.3–22 times compared to state-of-the-art systems (e.g. IBM's Mirage and Hemera) with significant VMI publishing and slight retrieval performance improvement.

1. Introduction

The evolving Cloud architecture [5, 11, 38, 42] requires efficient and scalable on-demand provisioning [8, 23, 41] and management of time-critical computing services [47, 48] over a federated [35] and heterogeneous infrastructure. Moreover, with the recent advent of the Edge and IoT technologies [11, 38] and their essential integration with the Cloud, the requirement for efficient management of the computing services is even higher. In this context, virtualization [2, 34] emerged as a key technology for enabling and provisioning of such computing services. One common virtualization technique that facilitates the deployment of computing services is the *virtual machine (VM)* [10, 12, 39, 40], instantiated using a user-created template called *VM image (VMI)* [19]. Such VMIs comprise an operating system (OS) and user-specific customized software package(s). However, the ever increasing number with size of each VMI in the magnitude of gigabytes induce important management issues such as VMI sprawl [33], hindering the elastic resource management and provisioning processes. For example, Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) alone consists of more than 30,000 public VMIs [3], where typical operations like cloning, versioning, sharing, storing and transforming

VMIs in dedicated repositories introduce a high amount of storage redundancy and maintenance costs.

To solve VMI management challenges such as sprawl, prior research primarily focused on leveraging *VMI deduplication* [20, 25, 28] and caching [16, 29, 32, 43] by identifying similar byte segments [15, 18, 30]. Such techniques optimize the VMI storage and reduce redundant content by up to 80%, but limit the benefits of virtualization, such as stronger isolation between software packages, and a provenance record of changes and reusable functionality at the VMI at semantic level [33]. Nevertheless, recent works such as IBM's Mirage [33] and Hemera [21] improved upon the previous studies and explored VMI management at a more fine grained file system level. Mirage employs a file system-based VMI repository that maps file names to content descriptors by a manifest, and use a data store to hold the content. In contrast, the Hemera follows a hybrid file system and database-oriented approach that transforms the VMI operations into database operations based on SQL queries. Both systems improve upon the VMI sprawl, but with significant VMI publishing and retrieval overheads due to costly data deduplication and read-write operations over thousand of files with varying sizes in a VMI repository.

The essential need is to explore a VMI management solution that exploits *semantic similarity* [6] to decompose VMIs at a functional level with low publishing and similarity computation overheads. This results in the creation of functional blocks composed of base images and various reusable software packages among different VMIs. We propose in this paper such a technique based on three important steps: (1)

*Corresponding author.

✉ nishant@itec.aau.at (N. Saurabh); shajulin@iitkottayam.ac.in (S. Benedict); jbarbosa@fe.up.pt (J.G. Barbosa); radu@itec.aau.at (R. Prodan)

ORCID(s): 0000-0002-1926-4693 (N. Saurabh); 0000-0002-2543-2710 (S. Benedict); 0000-0003-4135-2347 (J.G. Barbosa); 0000-0002-8247-5426 (R. Prodan)

defining and computing the semantic similarity between the VMIs based on their functionality, (2) splitting the VMIs into base image and software packages, thus avoiding storing of semantically redundant data, and (3) semantic assembling of base images with various software packages into fully functional VMIs with improved retrieval performance.

To address these challenges, we design a novel tool called *Expelliarmus* that represents a VMI and its components as a structured graph [1], presenting the functional requirements between the base image and different software packages. For each VMI semantic graph, it extracts two induced subgraphs, called the base image subgraph and software package subgraph. Their purpose is to merge several semantically similar VMIs into one VMI master graph, clustering their software packages with a semantically similar base image. This approach reduces the similarity computation overhead by comparing every VMI to the master graph instead of multiple individual VMI graphs. To facilitate the semantic aware decomposition, we employ techniques to only extract the unique software packages not yet available in the repository. Moreover, we devise a base image selection algorithm and define a novel semantic compatibility metric to select from a pool of semantically similar base images the one that is functionally compatible to existing software packages replacing the redundant ones. Our approach also provide means for VMI assembly, either with identical uploaded software packages or compatible with a base image already existing in the repository. To study the benefits of semantically-aware VMI management, we performed a series of experiments using a representative set of synthetic Linux-based VMIs. The results demonstrate that *Expelliarmus* optimizes the storage cost with significant VMI publish and slight retrieval performance improvements compared to the related [21, 33] state-of-the-art solutions.

We summarize the contributions of this paper as follows:

- 1) A novel semantic model that represents VMIs as structured graphs and clusters them based on functionality with low similarity computation overheads;
- 2) A semantics-aware decomposition method of large VMIs without costly content deduplication;
- 3) An optimized VMI assembly method with semantically similar base image and selective package retrieval.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces some relevant background concepts and summarizes the related work. Section 3 presents the new model together with the VMI semantic representation, and formulates the VMI semantic similarity and compatibility metrics. Section 4 describes the architecture of the *Expelliarmus*, including the VMI publishing, base image selection and VMI retrieval components and underlying algorithms. Section 5 provides relevant implementation details and Section 6 presents the experimental results. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. Background

This section revisits common scenarios of VMI management including VMI upload, customization and storage in

Figure 1: VMI management scenarios in IaaS Cloud.

IaaS Clouds. We also discuss existing deduplication techniques for VMI management and review the related works.

2.1. VMI management in IaaS Clouds.

Recent years saw an increased popularity of IaaS Clouds resulting into an explosion in the number of VMIs. Typically, IaaS Cloud providers allow users to create, upload, customize and manipulate VMIs through a Web interface [21], and instantiate them upon request across the data center computing resources. The (large-sized) VMIs are typically stored in a centralized shared repository, as the limited memory and storage availability of computing resources makes it infeasible to store them locally. The increase in number of VMs with diverse software stack instantiated across the data centers require maintaining tens of thousand of VMIs [3]. Such scenarios pose efficient storage optimization challenges for Cloud providers due to increasing scale and complexity of VMI management systems.

Figure 1 depicts the VMI management scenario in IaaS Clouds. Initially, a user uploads and stores a VMI I_1 in a shared repository and instantiates it as a VM. Once the VM gathers a substantial amount of updates, its running state is captured and stored in the global storage as a different version. Other users may also request for I_1 , customize it and store it in addition to existing versions. Similarly, typical operations like cloning, customizing and transforming VMIs in dedicated shared repositories introduce a high amount of storage redundancy due to the similar stack of software packages and base images included in different VMIs. The maintenance costs arising due to this problem can be avoided by restricting users in creating and cloning a limited number of VMIs, however, such a strategy limits the benefits of the virtualization technology [33] and requires other optimizations.

2.2. Deduplication

Deduplication is getting increasingly popular in storage management systems [49]. Basically, data deduplication

is a compression technique that eliminates redundant data chunks and improves storage utilization. For example, [25] provides a comprehensive taxonomy to classify data deduplication techniques by segregating them along three functionalities: placement, timing, and algorithm. First, the placement-based deduplication [45] is performed either at the client (i.e. data origin), storage server or dedicated middleware appliance. The client placement performs deduplication at data origin and forwards the non-redundant data chunks to the storage server. On the other hand, the middleware appliance placement receives the data from the client, performs deduplication, and transfers it to the storage server. Second, the timing functionality classifies deduplication as in-band and out-of-band operations [37]. The in-band operations synchronously eliminate redundant data chunks for every IO write request, such that duplicate data is never stored. In contrast, the out-of-band operations, also referred as an asynchronous functionality, store the data and perform deduplication at regular intervals. Finally, algorithm-based deduplication techniques separated by granularity are classified into three groups: delta encoding, file-level and block-level. The delta encoding algorithm applies the `diff` function [13] and stores the difference between two files. The file-level algorithm [17] performs SHA1 and MD5 [7] hash functions to obtain and match the hash signatures of the file content. On the contrary, the block-level [22] granularity splits files into fixed [9, 24, 26] or variable-size [27] chunks and uses Rabin Fingerprint [4, 31] schemes to compute and match the hashes of different chunks. Interestingly, each of these deduplication methods possess a dependency over the others. The placement-based deduplication driven by resource utilization restricts the choices for timing and algorithm-based deduplication classifications because of their time-critical and large-scale content analysis requirements [25].

2.3. Deduplication for VMI management

To overcome VMI management challenges such as sprawl [33], it is imperative to understand and identify the pattern and level of similarity in different VMIs [15]. Essentially, VMI similarity is of two kinds: content and semantic-based [6]. The content similarity alludes to similar data chunks or files between VMIs, while semantic similarity is characterised by similar functionality (i.e at the OS and software packages level). Previous researches focused on identifying VMI content similarity using deduplication due to its wide adaptation in archiving systems [49], applied at the block and file-level. The block-level technique treats VMI as a byte-array and employs fixed or variable-size chunking schemes to leverage similarity and eliminate redundant data chunks. Prior works [16, 15] demonstrate the effectiveness of fixed-size over variable-size chunking to achieve a better compression ratio for optimized VMI storage. In contrast, file-level deduplication treat a VMI as a file system and remove files with redundant content.

2.4. Related work

One key factor affecting the performance of IaaS Cloud management systems is the rapidly increasing number and

size of each stored VMI exceeding multiple GB. This introduces critical challenges to VMI management such as VMI sprawl, and hence impacts elastic resource management and provisioning. Moreover, these VMIs are usually excessively similar with a high a high degree of redundancy, addressed in the community through deduplication.

Jin et al. [16] explored the effectiveness of the block-level deduplication, both with fixed and variable-size chunking using Rabin fingerprinting [31] schemes. They showed that VMIs with the same guest OS and different software packages share considerable amount of data. This study also emphasized that VMI deduplication at block level with fixed-size chunking is more efficient than variable-size chunking, detecting up to 70% of identical content between VMIs.

Jayram et al. [15] built upon similar work comparing different VMI deduplication techniques and provided metrics for estimating VMI similarity. Their study showed that appropriate chunk size selection is essential for the block-level deduplication factor used in similarity computation.

Zhao et al. [46] proposed a scalable VMI file system called Liquid that enables large-scale VM deployment through a fixed-size block-level deduplication with low storage consumption. The system also improves the IO performance with a peer-to-peer VMI sharing and distribution.

Chun-Ho et al. [28] took a step forward and proposed a VMI backup system based on a block-level reverse deduplication that removes duplicates from old VMIs, while keeping the new VMI layout as sequential as possible.

Xu et al. [43, 44] proposed a VMI backup system named Crab that also uses block-level deduplication, but implements an additional k-means clustering method to group VMIs and speedup the index lookup overhead.

Reimer et al. [33] and Ammons et al. [1] proposed a new VMI format called Mirage as structured data, and performed file system indexing together with file-level deduplication to improve the inventory control and VM deployment.

Liu et al. [21] also approached the VMI as structured data in a rigorous database structure called Hemera that, in contrast to the Mirage, transforms the VMI operations into database operations based on simple SQL queries.

All these works proposed optimization to VMI management and VMI deduplication at content-level with restricted possibility to identify and extract reusable functionalities. Although Mirage and Hemera use additional semantic data to access VMIs at a fine-grained file system level with significant VMI publishing and retrieval overheads.

We improve over these approaches on both aspects. Instead of splitting the VMI into chunks or files, we split a VMI at semantic level into a base image and one or more software packages stored only once in the repository. In contrast, the related approaches store additional non-redundant content of all base images. Moreover, we assemble the VMIs not necessarily with the same base image, but also with a semantically similar one, if possible. Finally, the semantic-aware optimization of VMI storage reduces the VMI size with significant publishing and retrieval performance improvements.

3. VMI semantic model

This section presents a formal model and a set of basic definitions essential to this work.

3.1. Virtual machine image (VMI)

A *virtual machine image (VMI)* $I = (BI, PS, DS, Data)$ consists of a *base image* BI with a standalone OS, a set of software packages PS and DS installed on top, ranging from database to application servers, and a set user data $Data$.

A *primary package set* PS is a suite of software packages eligible to be hosted on an OS within a VMI. We assume that every VMI consists of one or more primary packages, required by the user upon instantiation.

A *dependency package set* DS contains libraries or other packages internal or external to the OS of the base image, used to build or install the primary packages within the VMI.

The *Data* component corresponds to the *user data* (e.g. files, directories) not recognized by the guest OS package management (e.g. home directory in a Linux file system).

3.2. VMI semantic graph

The *VMI semantic graph* is a high-level intermediate representation expressing the rich VMI structure in terms of functional requirements and relationships between base image, primary packages, and dependency packages. The semantic graph of a VMI I as a directed cyclic graph $G_I = (V_I, E_I)$, where $V_I = BI \cup PS \cup DS$ is the set of vertices including the base image, primary and dependency packages, and $E_I \subseteq V_I \times V_I$ is the set of edges, where a direct edge $e = (v, v') \in E_I$ denotes a dependency of the base image, primary package, or dependency package v on v' .

Figure 2a shows a VMI semantic graph with a Debian base image, two primary packages (MariaDB and Tomcat8), and several dependency packages (i.e. bash, openjdk, gawk, libc6, dpkg, debconf, perl-base, ucf and coreutils). The libc, perl-base and dpkg packages have a cyclic dependency, meaning that they need to be provided and installed together.

3.3. VMI attributes

Each base image BI of a VMI I has a quadruple of *attributes* $attrs(BI) = (type, distro, ver, arch)$, expressing the guest OS type (e.g. Linux), its distribution (e.g. Debian), its version (e.g. 16.04), and its architecture (e.g. x86_64).

Each primary or dependency package $P \in PS \cup DS$ holds a quadruple of attribute information $attrs(P) = (pkg, ver, arch, size)$ about its name pkg (e.g. MariaDB), version (e.g. 2.5), architecture (e.g. multiarch), and size (e.g. 1056).

Further, we prohibit a VMI semantic graph $G_I = (V_I, E_I)$ to contain multiple packages with the same pkg attribute, i.e. $\forall (P_1, P_2) \in V_I, pkg(P_1) \neq pkg(P_2)$.

Table 1 summarizes the attributes associated to a VMI and its semantic graph.

(a) VMI semantic graph example.

(b) VMI primary package subgraph for the VMI semantic graph from Figure 2a. (c) Base image subgraph for the VMI semantic graph from Figure 2a.

Figure 2: VMI semantic graph, primary package subgraph, and base image subgraph example.

Table 1

Attributes of a VMI semantic graph $G_I = (BI, PS, DS, Data)$.

Semantic attribute	Example
$type : BI \mapsto String$	$type(BI) = "Linux"$
$distro : BI \mapsto String$	$distro(BI) = "debian"$
$ver : BI \mapsto String$	$ver(BI) = "16.04"$
$arch : BI \mapsto String$	$arch(I) = "x86_64"$
$pkg : PS \cup DS \mapsto String$	$pkg(P) = "Tomcat8"$
$ver : PS \cup DS \mapsto String$	$ver(P) = "8.1.1"$
$arch : PS \cup DS \mapsto String$	$arch(P) = "multiarch"$
$size : PS \cup DS \mapsto String$	$size(P) = "4096"$

3.4. Semantic graph union

We define the *union* of two semantic graphs $G_1 = (V_1, E_1)$ and $G_2 = (V_2, E_2)$ as a new semantic graph $G = G_1 \cup G_2$, where $G = (V_1 \cup V_2, E_1 \cup E_2)$. Two vertices $v_1 \in V_1$ and $v_2 \in V_2$ are equivalent and belong to the intersection of the vertex sets of the two semantic graphs ($v_1 \equiv v_2 \in V_1 \cap V_2$) if they have the same attributes: $attrs(v_1) = attrs(v_2)$.

3.5. VMI subgraphs

A *primary package subgraph* $G_I[PS]$ is an induced subgraph of the VMI semantic graph containing all primary packages $PS \subset V_I$ and dependency packages reachable from them as vertices:

$$G_I[PS] = \bigcup_{\forall P \in PS} G_I[P],$$

where $G_I[P]$ is the induced connected subgraph containing all packages reachable from a package P :

$$G_I[P] = (V_P, E_P), P \in V_P \subset I \wedge E_P \subset E_I$$

$$\forall (P_1, P_2) \in E \implies (P_1, P_2) \in E_P.$$

The number of connected components in $G_I[PS]$ is less than or equal to the cardinality of the set PS , such that all packages are reachable from the primary ones.

Figure 2b shows the primary package subgraph for the VMI semantic graph in Figure 2a with `Mariadb` and `Tomcat8` as primary packages.

A *base image subgraph* $G_I[BI]$ is the induced connected subgraph containing the base image and all dependency packages reachable from it:

$$G_I[BI] = (V_B, E_B), BI \in V_B \wedge V_B \subset V_I \setminus PS \wedge E_B \in E \wedge \forall (P_1, P_2) \in E \implies (P_1, P_2) \in E_B.$$

The base image subgraph does not include primary packages. Figure 2c shows the base image subgraph for the VMI semantic graph in Figure 2a with `Debian` as base image.

3.6. VMI semantic similarity

Let us consider two VMIs I_1 and I_2 with two semantic graphs $G_1(V_1, E_1)$ and $G_2(V_2, E_2)$. In this section, we define the similarity between two VMIs as a number in the $[0, 1]$ interval representing how similar the attributes of each vertex in G_1 and G_2 are to each other.

Initially, we define the *base image similarity* between two base images BI_1 and BI_2 as a binary digit with the value of 1 if the two images have the same attribute values and with the value of 0 otherwise:

$$sim_{BI}(BI_1, BI_2) = \begin{cases} 1, & attrs(BI_1) = attrs(BI_2), \\ 0, & attrs(BI_1) \neq attrs(BI_2). \end{cases}$$

Similarly, we define the *primary or dependency package similarity* between two packages P_1 and P_2 as 1 if they have the same name, version and architecture, as binary values:

$$sim_{pkg}(P_1, P_2) = \begin{cases} 1, & pkg(P_1) = pkg(P_2), \\ 0, & pkg(P_1) \neq pkg(P_2); \end{cases}$$

$$sim_{ver}(P_1, P_2) = \begin{cases} 1, & ver(P_1) = ver(P_2), \\ 0, & ver(P_1) \neq ver(P_2); \end{cases}$$

$$sim_{arch}(P_1, P_2) = \begin{cases} 1, & arch(P_1) = arch(P_2) \vee \\ & arch(P_1) = "all" \vee \\ & arch(P_2) = "all"; \\ 0, & otherwise; \end{cases}$$

$$sim_P(P_1, P_2) = \prod_{\forall attr \in \{pkg, ver, arch\}} sim_{attr}(P_1, P_2).$$

An architecture attribute of “all” means that the package is portable and available on base images with any architecture.

Further, we compute the *size similarity* between two packages P_1 and P_2 as the ratio between the maximum size of the two packages divided by maximum size of all packages from both VMIs, where the size denotes the amount of

disk space consumed by a software package within a VMI, including any software package updates:

$$sim_{size}(P_1, P_2) = \frac{\max\{size(P_1), size(P_2)\}}{\max_{\forall P \in V_1 \cup V_2} \{size(P)\}}.$$

This allows us to compute a weighted composition of content and semantic similarity [6] of packages within two VMIs.

Finally, we model the *VMI semantic similarity* between two semantic graphs G_1 and G_2 based on the Jaccard index [14], also known as intersection over union. We formulate it as a product of the similarity between base images and the matched software packages with normalized package size in the numerator, and the union of all packages in both VMIs in the denominator:

$$Sim_G(G_1, G_2) = sim_{BI}(BI_1, BI_2) \cdot \frac{\sum_{\forall (P_1, P_2) \in V_1 \times V_2} sim_{size}(P_1, P_2) \cdot sim_P(P_1, P_2)}{\sum_{\forall (P_1, P_2) \in V_1 \times V_2} sim_{size}(P_1, P_2)}.$$

3.7. Semantic compatibility

We define the *semantic compatibility* between a base image subgraph $G_I(BI) = (V_{BI}, E_{BI})$ and a primary package subgraph $G_I(PS) = (V_{PS}, E_{PS})$ as the product of the similarities of their packages with a homonym *pkg* attribute:

$$comp(G_I[BI], G_I[PS]) = \prod_{\substack{\forall (P_1, P_2) \in V_{BI} \times V_{PS} \\ \wedge pkg(P_1) = pkg(P_2)}} sim_P(P_1, P_2).$$

If the semantic compatibility is 1, the primary packages can be installed and used together with the base image. Otherwise they are incompatible.

3.8. VMI master graph

A *VMI master graph* $G_M[T, D, V, A]$ represents all VMIs with the same type, distribution, version and architecture base image attributes (T, D, V, A) stored in the repository. The master graph contains one single base image subgraph semantically compatible to all primary package subgraphs of the VMIs represented in the master graph. The purpose of the VMI master graph is to reduce the similarity computation overhead between multiple VMI semantic graphs with one single master graph similarity comparison. We therefore model the master graph as the union of one base image and one or more primary package subgraphs originating from VMIs with the same base image attributes:

$$G_M[T, D, V, A] = \bigcup_{\substack{\forall I \in Repo \wedge \\ attrs(BI) = (T, D, V, A) \wedge \\ comp(G_I[BI], G_I[PS]) = 1}} (G_I[BI] \cup G_I[PS]).$$

4. Semantic-centric VMI Management

This section describes the architecture of Expelliarmus, including its VMI publishing and retrieval algorithms.

Figure 3: Expelliarmus architecture and VMI management.

4.1. Architecture overview

Figure 3 describes the architecture of Expelliarmus through a use-case in which multiple users initially upload a VMI for storage in a proprietary Cloud image repository. Afterwards, they download and instantiate the VMI multiple times at various Cloud locations. Every time the users update a VMI and store it in the image repository, they introduce a considerable amount of redundancy and other management costs in terms of VMI publishing and retrieval, hindering the elastic provisioning and deployment process. At the same time, different VMIs with varying software packages uploaded by different users could also be composed of semantically similar base images and software packages. Expelliarmus semantically decomposes VMIs in reusable fragments so that similar software packages and base images within different VMIs are stored only once with reduced redundancy, publishing and retrieval overheads.

The publishing, storage and retrieval of a VMI in Expelliarmus takes place using the following steps (see Figure 3):

- 1) The user uploads a VMI and a list of primary packages for storage in the VMI repository;
- 2) The semantic analyzer creates a VMI semantic graph and computes its semantic similarity with other VMIs;
- 3) To publish the VMI, the decomposer splits a VMI into a base image and multiple software packages exploiting the semantic similarity with other VMIs for storing only non-redundant packages and base images;

- 4) The user requests the retrieval of a VMI;
- 5) The VMI assembler assembles the VMI according to the user request and delivers it.

4.2. VMI semantic analyzer

The semantic analyzer takes the VMI and the primary package list as input and constructs the semantic graph, following the model defined in Section 3.2. This automates the process of optimizing and accessing semantic similarity of monolithic VMIs without detailed content analysis, instead caching a subset of VMI semantic data in the form of a graph.

The semantic analyzer creates a graph G_I for every uploaded VMI I along with a subgraph representation of the corresponding primary packages and base image. Afterwards, it compares the newly uploaded VMI with the appropriate master graph G_M with the same type, distribution, version and architecture attributes, previously stored in the repository according to the semantic similarity defined in Section 3.6. Every VMI master graph is specific to a characteristic base image with one or more semantically compatible primary package subgraphs. If no such master graph exists in the repository, the semantic analyzer forwards the VMI to the decomposer.

4.3. VMI decomposer

The VMI decomposer splits a VMI into a base image and different software packages, exploiting semantic similarity such that only non-redundant software packages and

base images are stored. To achieve this, the decomposer employs two algorithms: VMI publishing (Algorithm 1) and base image selection (Algorithm 2).

4.3.1. VMI publishing algorithm

Algorithm 1 outlines the step-wise VMI publishing process. The algorithm takes as input a VMI I , its semantic graph G_I , a VMI repository, and list of primary packages PS . Initially, the algorithm extracts the VMI's primary package subgraph $G_I[PS]$ in line 1. Afterwards, it iterates each primary package in the subgraph, checks if it exists in the repository with same semantic attributes (lines 2 – 5) and, if it does not exist, stores it (line 4). After checking all primary subgraph packages, the algorithm stores the user data in line 6. Next, line 8 removes the primary packages from the VMI, including the user data and the dependency packages not used by any software package still within the VMI (lines 10 – 11). At this point, the VMI contains only the base image BI (line 12) with all its required software packages already stored in the repository. To prevent redundant storage of the same base image, a base image selection algorithm (see Algorithm 2 in Section 4.3.2) called at line 14 returns a similar base image, together with a list of base images stored in the repository that are no longer required. If Algorithm 2 returns the current base image, we update the repository along with the corresponding new master graph in lines 15 – 17. However, if Algorithm 2 returns another already stored base image, line 19 retrieves its master graph from the repository and updates the retrieved master graph with the primary package subgraph $G_I[PS]$ in line 21. Algorithm 2 also returns a list of base images that can be replaced with the selected base image. Line 22 – 28 iterates over this list and line 23 retrieves the master graph for each replaceable base image from the repository. Each retrieved master graph corresponding to a base image in the list is a union of a base image subgraph and several primary package subgraphs. Lines 24 – 26 iterate over the primary packages in each master graph and update the master graph of the selected base image G_M with the extracted primary package subgraph (line 25). Line 27 removes the obsolete base images and line 29 updates the master graph in the repository.

4.3.2. Base image selection algorithm

As a part of the VMI publishing, Algorithm 2 returns an appropriate base image and a list of previously stored base images that are no longer needed. The selected base image is semantically compatible with the primary packages corresponding to the base images in the list. The algorithm takes as input a base image BI , the primary package subgraph $G_I[PS]$ of an image I , and a VMI repository $repo$. Initially, line 1 initializes a triplet list with the base image of a VMI I , the base image subgraph, and the primary package subgraph. Afterwards, line 3 retrieves the list of all base images stored in the repository. Lines 4 – 12 iterate over the list of stored base images, and gets the corresponding base image subgraph and master graph in lines 5 and 6. Next, the

Algorithm 1: VMI publishing algorithm.

```

Input :  $I = (BI, PS, DS, Data)$ : VMI;  $G_I$ : semantic graph of VMI  $I$ ;
          $PS$ : primary package set;  $repo$ : VMI repository
1  $G_I[PS] = (V_p, E_p) \leftarrow \text{extractSubGraph}(G_I)$ 
2 forall  $P \in V_p$  do
3   | if  $\neg \text{exists}(P, repo)$  then
4   |   |  $\text{store}(P, repo)$ 
5   end
6  $\text{store}(Data, repo)$ 
7 forall  $P \in PS$  do
8   |  $\text{remove}(P, I)$ 
9 end
10  $\text{removeUnusedDependencies}(I)$ 
11  $\text{remove}(Data, I)$ 
12  $BI \leftarrow I$ 
13  $G_I[BI] \leftarrow \text{createSubGraph}(BI)$ 
14  $(base, list) \leftarrow \text{selectBaseImage}(BI, G_I[BI], G_I[PS], repo)$ 
15 if  $base = BI$  then
16   |  $G_M \leftarrow \text{createMasterGraph}(G_I[BI])$ 
17   |  $\text{store}(BI, repo)$ ;
18 else
19   |  $G_M \leftarrow \text{getMasterGraph}(base, repo)$ 
20 end
21  $G_M \leftarrow G_M \cup G_I[PS]$ 
22 forall  $b \in list$  do
23   |  $G_{Mb} \leftarrow \text{getMasterGraph}(b, repo)$ 
24   | forall  $P \in G_{Mb}$  do
25   |   |  $G_M \leftarrow G_M \cup \text{extractSubGraph}(G_{Mb}, P)$ 
26   |   end
27   |  $\text{remove}(b, repo)$ 
28 end
29  $\text{update}(G_M, repo)$ 

```

algorithm checks the semantic similarity between the base image BI and the stored base images in line 7. If the semantic similarity between the base images exist, line 9 extracts each primary package subgraph from the master graph, while line 10 adds the stored base image, its base image subgraph, and the primary package subgraphs into a triplet list. Afterwards, lines 13 – 26 iterate over all base images in this triplet list. For each current base image, the algorithm adds first all base images BI_j that are not identical but similar to BI_i , and BI_i is semantically compatible (see Section 3.7) to their primary packages into the replace list (see lines 15 – 18, meaning that the current base image BI_i can replace all the base images in its replace list). If the replace list is not empty (line 20), line 23 computes the total size of all packages of the base image BI_i in the replace list. Finally, line 25 adds the base image, the replace list, and the total size of its packages into a new quadruple list. The fourth boolean component (i.e. $BI_i = BI$) of the quadruple indicates whether this base image is new or already existed in the repository. Once this procedure completes for all base images in the triplet list, line 27 sorts the generated quadruples list based on three criteria: the replace list size (i.e. the more replaced base images, the better), the total size of its packages (the smaller, the better), and existence of a similar base image in the repository (i.e. no unnecessary storage). Lines 29 – 32 iterate over the sorted quadruples list, and extract the base image and its replace list in line 29. Finally, it checks the first quadruple that either specifies the base image BI or exists in the replace list in line 30 and returns it in line 31. If no quadruple exists with the base image BI , line 33 returns it with an empty replace list.

Algorithm 2: Base image selection algorithm.

Input : BI : remaining base image after decomposition; $G_I[BI]$: base image subgraph; $G_I[PS]$: primary package subgraph; $repo$: VMI repository

```
1 list3  $\leftarrow [(BI, G_I[BI], G_I[PS])]$ 
2 list4  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3 baseList  $\leftarrow$  getBaseImageList(repo)
4 forall  $b \in$  baseList do
5    $G_I[b] \leftarrow$  getSubGraph( $b, repo$ )
6    $G_{Mb} \leftarrow$  getMasterGraph( $b, repo$ );
7   if  $sim_{BI}(BI, b) = 1$  then
8     forall  $P \in G_{Mb}$  do
9        $G_I[P] \leftarrow$  extractSubGraph( $G_{Mb}, P$ )
10      list3  $\leftarrow$  list3  $\cup \{(b, G_I[b], G_I[P])\}$ 
11    end
12  end
13 forall  $i \in$  list3 do
14   ( $BI_i, G_I[BI_i], G_I[PS_i]$ )  $\leftarrow i$ 
15   forall  $j \neq i \in$  list3 do
16     ( $BI_j, G_I[BI_j], G_I[PS_j]$ )  $\leftarrow j$ 
17     if  $BI_i \neq BI_j \wedge comp(G_I[BI_i], G_I[PS_j]) = 1$  then
18       replaceList  $\leftarrow$  replaceList  $\cup \{BI_j\}$ 
19   end
20   if replaceList  $\neq \emptyset$  then
21     size  $\leftarrow 0$ 
22     forall  $P \in G_I[BI_i]$  do
23       size  $\leftarrow$  size + size( $P$ );
24     end
25     list4  $\leftarrow$  list4  $\cup \{(BI_i, replaceList, size, BI = BI_i)\}$ 
26  end
27 list4  $\leftarrow$  sort(list4)
28 forall  $i \in$  list4 do
29   ( $BI_i, replaceList, \_, \_$ )  $\leftarrow i$ 
30   if  $BI_i = BI \vee BI \in$  replaceList then
31     return ( $BI_i, replaceList$ )
32  end
33 return ( $BI, \emptyset$ )
```

4.4. VMI assembler

Expelliarmus enables VMI assembly either with identical or with differing functionality, provided that the requested packages exist in the repository. For this, the VMI assembler employs a VMI retrieval algorithm (Algorithm 3) that processes the requests for assembly and deployment.

4.4.1. VMI retrieval algorithm

Algorithm 3 represents the stepwise VMI retrieval process with two input parameters: a (nonexistent) VMI I identified by its base image BI and primary package set PS , and a VMI repository $repo$. Initially, line 1 obtains the base image and primary package subgraphs from the repository. If they exist and are compatible (line 2), line 3 retrieves the base image BI from the repository and resets it to an initial state in line 4. Line 5 imports the user data into the VMI I . Lines 6 – 10 iterate over each vertex in the primary package subgraph and check their existence in the base image subgraph in line 7. If the vertex does not exist, line 8 adds the vertex into the primary package set PS . Finally, the VMI's guest OS package manager installs the primary packages in line 12 by importing the required software packages (including primary and dependency packages), if necessary (see Section 5.1 and 5.4 for software package installation details). Line 15 returns the assembled VMI.

Algorithm 3: VMI retrieval algorithm.

Input : $I = (BI, PS, _, _, Data)$: VMI; $repo$: VMI repository

```
1 ( $G_I[BI], G_I[PS]$ )  $\leftarrow$  getSubGraph( $I, repo$ )
2 if  $G_I[BI] \neq \text{NULL} \wedge G_I[PS] \neq \text{NULL} \wedge comp(G_I[BI], G_I[PS]) = 1$ 
3   then
4      $BI \leftarrow$  getBaseImage( $id, G_I[BI], repo$ )
5     resetVMI( $BI$ )
6     import( $Data, I$ )
7     forall  $P \in G_I[PS]$  do
8       if  $P \notin G_I[BI]$  then
9          $PS \leftarrow PS \cup P$ 
10      end
11    end
12    forall  $P \in PS$  do
13      install( $P, I$ );
14    end
15  end
16 return  $I$ 
```

5. Implementation

We implemented Expelliarmus in Python and publicly released in GitHub¹ the complete source code of our implementation, including the reproducibility artifact of the experimental validation. In the following, we briefly discuss the implementation details of Expelliarmus with respect to the VMI manipulation, semantic graph creation, VMI publishing and retrieval, currently limited to Linux VMIs only.

5.1. VMI access

Expelliarmus uses the `libguestfs`² library to access, manipulate and modify VMIs for performing VMI publishing and retrieval including software packages installation (see Section 5.3 and 5.4). Apart from performing modifications to a VMI file system, `libguestfs` provides access to the guest OS through its virtual appliance without instantiating the entire VMI. To achieve this, `libguestfs` configures and launches a `guestfs` handle that provides an interface to access the VMIs. The `guestfs` handle creates a child process running a tiny `supermin` virtual appliance (similar to a VM), usually around 100 kB in size, instantiated on-the-fly in a fraction of a second. The appliance integrated with `qemu`³ (i.e. a generic machine emulator and virtualizer) holds the Linux kernel and runs as a `guestfsd` daemon to facilitate the communication with `libguestfs` functionalities. This attaches the specified VMI to the `qemu` process. Subsequently, the system accesses the VMI and its guest OS without instantiating it through the `guestfsd` daemon.

5.2. VMI graph representation

We represent VMIs according to semantic principles described in Section 3.2 and store them in graph data structure using the Python-based `networkx`⁴ module, implemented depending upon the suitable package management of the guest OS (e.g. APT or DNF). We execute the package management commands through `libguestfs` on the VMI guest OS to fetch the required semantic information (e.g. architecture, ver-

¹<https://github.com/ExpelliarmusSuperComp/Expelliarmus>

²<http://libguestfs.org>

³<https://www.qemu.org/>

⁴<https://networkx.github.io/>

Table 2
Experimental setup.

Parameters	Value
OS kernel version	5.0.0-31
Processors	64
L1 cache	32 k
L2 cache	1024 k
L3 cache	22 528 k
RAM	384 GB DDR4
Storage capacity	9.6 TB SSD

sion) about the base image, and installed software and dependency packages associated to graph vertices and edges.

5.3. VMI publishing

VMI publishing comprises a decomposition process, accomplished by recreating the binary package (e.g. .deb distribution files) for the required software packages and utilizing the `libguestfs` calls to export them to the VMI repository. Furthermore, we remove the specific package binaries, configurations and the dependency packages no longer required in the VMI, followed by cleaning up the cached repository files. Finally, we employ the base image selection algorithm to select the appropriate base image for storage.

5.4. VMI retrieval

VMI retrieval comprises the assembly procedure, achieved by first resetting the base image using the `virt-sysprep` tool (part of `libguestfs`), followed by importing software packages and specific user data into the VMI. Furthermore, we scan each imported software package to create the meta-data readable by the package manager. Afterwards, we add a custom repository configuration file (i.e. pointer to software packages in the local repository) that enables the VMI’s guest OS package management to install packages from the local repository instead of the online ones. For software package installation, we execute the package management commands through `libguestfs` on the VMI guest OS without instantiating the entire VMI (see Section 5.1). Finally, we remove the local temporary repository including the custom configuration, and restore the default repository configuration files (i.e. pointer to online package management repository).

6. Experimental Results

We evaluated Expelliarmus on an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 5218 server at 2.30 GHz running Ubuntu 18.04 (x86_64) OS, with an attached 9.6 TB SSD disk acting as a VMI repository. Table 2 displays further experimental testbed details. We used the `SQLite`⁵ database engine, suitable for managing VMI meta-data due to its self-contained, serverless, and zero configuration characteristics. In principle, our system is capable of running on any Linux-based OS with support for `libguestfs`, `qemu` and `SQLite` software tools.

⁵<https://www.sqlite.org/index.html>

6.1. Experimental VMI sets

In the lack of any public VMI management benchmark, we evaluated our approach using a synthetic VMI set based on the Ubuntu Linux distribution with software packages recognized by the package management tools. We will address the management of VMIs composed of software packages recognized by non-package management tools (e.g. `pip`, `snap`) or installed through compiled source code in future work. We create each VMI using `virt-builder`⁶, an efficient tool for building a variety of images for local and Cloud use. The minimal script to create an experimental image is available in the GitHub code repository¹. For a fair comparison, the evaluation set includes four VMIs used in two previous studies and in the same configuration [1, 21], namely Mini, Base, Desktop, and IDE. The VMI set also includes 38 images with a similar software stack as provided at the Amazon Web Services portal⁷ for free and enterprise use, to provide a representative set of Cloud images for evaluation:

- 1) *Mini* images with minimal non-desktop installation of the Ubuntu Linux distribution;
- 2) *Base* images with the LAPP software stack;
- 3) *Desktop* images with X Windows and desktop productivity tools, including LAPP and FTP/NFS servers;
- 4) *IDE* image with an integrated development environment including Eclipse, JDK, and Python;
- 5) *Infrastructure* images with application servers (e.g. Redis, SQLite, Celery, httpd, Nginx, Tornado, Yarn, Flower, Gluster-FS, Samba, MariaDB, Solr, MySQL, XDM, Neo4j, Lamp, Lemp, Jenkins, Tomcat, MongoDB, CouchDB, Django, RabbitMQ, Cassandra, PostgreSQL, ELK), and project management tools (i.e. ownCloud).
- 6) *DevOps* images with infrastructure-as-code tools (e.g. Puppet, Vagrant), continuous monitoring and analytic servers (i.e. Elastic Search, Kibana, and Logstash), and automated application management solutions (i.e. Docker, and Kubernetes).

Table 3 lists the characteristics of the VMIs including their mounted disk use, number of files in their file system, semantic similarity, and publishing and retrieval times. We created the VMIs from scratch as an extension to the VMI list in [36]. We assumed that the repository is initially empty and the VMIs were randomly uploaded for the first execution. We average the evaluation results across five trials, as their variance is relatively small in all experiments. To maintain the uniformity of the evaluation over the five trials, we performed the remaining four executions in the same sequence listed in Table 3. Additionally, we used 500 VMIs to demonstrate the scalability of Expelliarmus, derived from the 42 VMIs listed in Table 3 through cloning and sprawling operations (i.e. software installation and update).

We considered three *evaluation scenarios* that sequentially store a number of VMIs, as follows:

- 1) *SMALL* considers four VMIs from previous studies [1, 21] for direct comparison: Mini, Base, Desktop, IDE;

⁶<http://libguestfs.org/virt-builder.1.html>

⁷<https://aws.amazon.com/marketplace>

(a) SMALL (4 VMIs).

(b) LARGE (42 VMIs).

(c) IDE (50 IDE VMIs).

Figure 4: Repository size growth for three evaluation scenarios.**Table 3**
LARGE VMI experimental set characteristics.

VMI number	VMI name	Mounted size [GB]	Number of files	Similarity [Sim_G]	Publishing time [s]	Retrieval time [s]
1	Mini	1.63342	65011	0	26.13	12.77
2	Redis	1.63653	65081	0.97	7.79	12.86
3	Sqlite	1.63848	65030	0.91	11.55	12.60
4	Celery	1.64746	66151	0.93	8.21	15.08
5	OpenVPN	1.64166	65331	0.97	8.45	12.96
6	Apache-httpd	1.64752	66014	0.69	34.29	15.04
7	Nginx	1.65350	65351	0.88	9.63	14.36
8	Tornado	1.67456	67042	0.71	11.68	14.59
9	Yarn	1.66278	65336	0.80	11.06	14.16
10	Postgre SQL	1.69201	67355	0.86	16.08	16.60
11	Django	1.69122	75530	0.71	15.23	14.37
12	Flower	1.70843	69791	0.76	13.61	16.76
13	Gluster-FS	1.69744	67640	0.75	19.95	23.80
14	CouchDB	1.71215	67388	0.76	20.25	18.82
15	Vagrant	1.70739	69024	0.79	15.82	15.67
16	Samba	1.73431	68346	0.72	23.78	16.79
17	Tomcat	1.80853	66145	0.40	44.53	18.93
18	MariaDB	1.79785	66038	0.35	32.01	24.13
19	Apache Solr	1.88867	67916	0.83	16.36	22.47
20	MySQL	1.82855	66117	0.42	37.20	20.94
21	Ethereum	1.83135	65357	0.38	62.38	19.26
22	Own Cloud	1.94165	83042	0.61	53.81	25.72
23	XDM	1.82452	66069	0.98	4.32	15.07
24	MongoDB	1.88494	65310	0.18	98.06	19.51
25	Puppet	2.03308	78257	0.57	56.81	23.98
26	Docker-env	1.95758	67005	0.30	113.36	21.11
27	VirtualBox	1.95391	68489	0.70	67.46	48.37
28	Cassandra	2.01068	69317	0.50	108.78	34.01
29	Base	1.95037	86402	0.90	27.03	34.76
30	Jenkins	2.13690	68834	0.86	34.55	33.85
31	Elastic Search	2.05871	69256	0.85	33.06	34.26
32	Desktop	2.11517	91280	0.92	32.53	43.84
33	Lamp	2.27398	100060	0.98	6.98	26.25
34	Lemp	2.28131	99580	0.98	9.45	25.64
35	Neo4J	2.26873	67553	0.72	63.36	41.00
36	RabbitMQ	2.21447	87070	0.84	33.18	30.65
37	Kibana	2.32360	108798	0.70	109.81	30.82
38	Logstash	2.34014	83757	0.72	88.51	31.17
39	IDE	2.38635	73820	0.71	72.87	44.46
40	DevOps toolbox	2.42687	86042	0.91	32.42	63.16
41	Kubernetes	2.46661	68879	0.15	254.69	29.70
42	ELK-Stack	2.83361	125340	0.98	11.15	34.30

- 2) *LARGE* considers the 42 VMIs listed in Table 3 to show the growth of repository at larger-scale.
- 3) *IDE* considers 50 IDE images obtained by successive builds, similar to previous studies [1, 21].

6.2. VMI repository optimization

For each scenario, we compared the Expelliarmus storage optimization with the following VMI encoding schemes:

- 1) *Qcow2* format with no compression⁸;
- 2) *Qcow2 + Gzip* compressed format⁹;
- 3) *Mirage* MIF [1] format with a manifest file to manage VMI descriptors and store VMIs in a global data store;
- 4) *Hemera* [21] format with a hybrid file system and database-oriented approach for managing VMI content.

Figure 4a shows the cumulative repository growth for the *SMALL* scenario. On a repository that stores only four images with a cumulative size of 8.08 GB in *Qcow2* format, Expelliarmus performs better requiring only 2.05 GB compared to 3.08 GB for images compressed with Gzip, and to 3.17 GB for *Mirage* and *Hemera* systems.

Figure 4b estimates the performance of these systems for the *LARGE* scenario. For a cumulative repository size of 81.61 GB in the *Qcow2* format, Expelliarmus requires 2.95 GB, while *Mirage* and *Hemera* perform again similarly requiring 15.41 GB. In this scenario, the storage cost for *Qcow2* images compressed with Gzip is worse requiring 32.43 GB. An important observation from Figure 4a and Figure 4b is the improved performance of *Mirage*, *Hemera* and Expelliarmus with increasing number of VMIs in the repository over Gzip. The performance of *Mirage* and *Hemera* is due to the file-level deduplication that stores common files from the same and different VMIs only once. In contrast, Expelliarmus not only relies on deduplicating similar software packages, but also optimizes the VMI storage by removing software packages not dependent on the primary ones, an opportunity not captured by *Mirage* and *Hemera*. Moreover, Expelliarmus's base image selection reduces the storage by selecting one from a pool of semantically similar base images, while *Mirage* and *Hemera* store additional non-redundant content of other base images. Evidently, the base image is a major contributor to the higher repository size.

The advantage of Expelliarmus is better captured by the *IDE* scenario in Figure 4c. For a cumulative repository size of 120.61 GB, Expelliarmus requires 2.62 GB, while *Mirage* and *Hemera*-based storage require 5.96 GB. The storage size for the Gzip scheme is even higher, requiring 57 GB. In this

⁸<https://people.gnome.org/~markmc/qcow-image-format.html>

⁹<https://www.gzip.org/>

(a) SMALL (4 VMIs).

(b) Expelliarmus LARGE (42 VMIs).

(c) LARGE (42 VMIs).

Figure 5: VMI publishing analysis.

scenario, Expelliarmus performs 22 times better than Gzip, and 2.3 times better than Mirage and Hemera, which in turn perform 9.5 times better than Gzip.

6.3. VMI publishing

We evaluate the performance of publishing a VMI, as the decomposition comprising the time to create a `guestfs` handle for VMI access, export semantically unique software packages, remove the unused software packages, and select the compatible base image. On the contrary, the time to retrieve a VMI reflects the assembly comprising the time to create a `guestfs` handle, copy the appropriate base image to the local repository, reset the VMI, and import the software packages. We evaluate the VMI publishing for two scenarios, SMALL and LARGE, introduced in Section 6.1.

For the SMALL scenario, Figure 5a shows that Expel-

liarmus optimizes not only the storage cost, but also publishes VMI faster than Mirage and Hemera. The VMI publishing time in Expelliarmus depends not only on the mounted VMI size, but also on the software packages installation size, as the space required by the software package to be installed on a disk, which is always larger than in the `.deb` or `.rpm` formats. The different software packages with varying installation sizes largely affect the time to create a binary software package (e.g. `.deb`) resulting in a higher export time to the repository. The total installation size of the exported software packages for the Base VMI is the largest, and hence requires more time to publish in Expelliarmus compared to other images. In contrast, Mirage and Hemera require longer time for the Desktop VMI, as the publishing time is proportional to the mounted size and the file sizes within a VMI.

Another reason for faster VMI publishing compared to the file system-based approaches is the lower deduplication overheads. Mirage and Hemera require matching content over thousands of files incurring time penalties in the range of seconds to few minutes. In contrast, Expelliarmus relies on VMI semantic graphs for similarity computation and semantic clustering of similar VMIs into a master graph, which allows the comparison of new VMIs with a single master graph instead of multiple VMIs. The similarity computation in Expelliarmus incurs time penalties in the order of less than 100 ms for each VMI, which eradicates a large share of VMI publishing overhead with low similarity computation cost.

The primary factors contributing to the VMI publishing time in Expelliarmus are better represented by the LARGE scenario over a repository with 42 VMIs, successively added as listed in Table 3. Figure 5b shows the publishing time for Expelliarmus as a combination of three operations: `guestfs` handler creation, compatible base image selection, and exporting semantically unique software packages. The first two operations share nearly equal time for publishing different VMIs, while the export time invariably differs. As already explained, VMI publishing in Expelliarmus depends upon the installation size of the exported software packages, which is highest in case of Kubernetes VMI.

Figure 5c compares the VMI publishing times for the LARGE scenario, using an additional variant of Expelliarmus called *semantic decomposition* that exports all the required software packages without considering semantic similarity. Expelliarmus publishes again VMIs faster than Mirage, Hemera, and its own variant semantic decomposition. While the ELK VMI required the longest publishing time in Mirage and Hemera due to its mounted size and large number of files (more than 120 thousand), the Kubernetes VMI had the longest publishing time in Expelliarmus due to the highest installation size of the exported software packages. The longest publishing time for semantic decomposition has ELK VMI, while Expelliarmus performed better as it only exports the software packages that do not exist in the repository. As the similarity computation overhead in Expelliarmus is very low, the VMI publishing time is mostly dependent on exporting the software packages. However, the more VMIs are uploaded to the repository, the less software

(a) Expelliarmus breakdown.

(b) Retrieval time comparison.

Figure 6: VMI retrieval in LARGE scenario (42 VMIs).

packages are exported by Expelliarmus with lower publishing time compared to semantic decomposition.

6.4. VMI retrieval

Figure 6a shows the VMI retrieval in Expelliarmus for the LARGE scenario as a composition of four operations: copy the base image from the repository, create the `guestfs` handler, reset the VMI, and import the required software packages into a VMI. The first three operations share nearly equal time for different VMIs, while the import time invariably differs. Evidently, the VMI retrieval in Expelliarmus depends on the installation size of the imported packages, which is highest in the case of DevOps toolbox VMI.

Figure 6b compares the VMI retrieval time, which is fastest for Hemera and Expelliarmus than Mirage. Expelliarmus’s better performance is due to selective package retrieval and importing into a VMI that significantly reduces the total size read from the repository. Mirage’s VMI retrieval is worse because it retrieves more data by reading many files instead of reading linearly through one file, and is also inefficient in reading small files (below 1 MB) from file system-based repository. Hemera improves this overhead by taking a hybrid approach that stores large files in the repository and small-sized files in the database, which optimizes VMI retrieval as the database handles small files much faster than the file system. Although Hemera performs slightly worse than Expelliarmus for most VMIs, the retrieval time of four VMIs (i.e. Lamp, Lemp, Kibana and ELK Stack) is considerably different in both cases. While Expelliarmus

retrieval takes 26.25 s, 25.64 s, 30.82 s, and 34.30 s for four VMIs, Hemera needs around three times longer (i.e. 78.22 s, 76.09 s, 86.58 s, and 106.86 s) due to increasingly large number of files (more than 100 thousand) and VMI mounted size.

6.5. Scalability

To study the scalability of Expelliarmus, we used additional 500 VMIs derived through cloning and sprawling operations from the 42 VMIs of the LARGE scenario listed in Table 3 in two experiments. The first experiment studied the VMI retrieval with the growing repository size, and the second explored the performance of parallel VMI retrieval. The scalability study ignored VMI publishing for two reasons. Firstly, VMI retrieval is the critical performance measure amongst the two operations for efficient and scalable provisioning of time-critical services [21]. Secondly, Expelliarmus does not support synchronized IO write operations for multiple concurrent VMI uploads (part of future work).

Figure 7a shows the retrieval time for four VMIs (i.e. DevOps Toolbox, Virtual Box, IDE, Neo4J) in Expelliarmus with the growing repository size in Qcow2 format. We selected these four VMIs due to their highest retrieval times amongst the 42 VMIs according to Figure 6b. In general, the increase in data repository size produces higher retrieval times inducing higher latency for disk IO operations [21]. Contrarily, VMI retrieval in Expelliarmus slightly changes by a few seconds with the growing number of VMIs and corresponding repository size. While the repository size exponentially grows to 1.2 TB in Qcow2 format for 500 VMIs, Expelliarmus’s repository size grows upto 3.84 GB and requires storing a fraction of updates with every additional VMI (see Section 6.2). Hence, leads to a moderate variance in VMI retrieval time across the large repository.

We study the performance of parallel VMI retrieval for provisioning a heterogeneous VM cluster with diverse software packages. We retrieved the 42 VMIs from the LARGE VMI set introduced in Section 6.1, in a repository with more than 500 VMIs of 1.2 TB in total. We parallelised the retrieval on an increasing number of processes, such that on p processes, every process assembled $\approx \lfloor \frac{42}{p} \rfloor$ VMIs. Figure 7b shows that the parallel retrieval time of the 42 VMIs decreases almost linearly until 10 processors. Assembling 42 VMIs on more than 10 processes that retrieve software packages in parallel generates an IO bottleneck on the SSD disk (see Table 2) and brings no more benefit to the retrieval process. This demonstrates that the parallel VMI retrieval depends on the storage disk performance, including storage disk access patterns [1] that limit its scalability.

7. Conclusion

We introduced Expelliarmus, a new VMI management system with a semantic-centric design for VMI storage with optimized VMI publish and retrieval. Different from the existing VMI management systems that ignore VMI semantics, Expelliarmus incorporates three features. First, it represents VMIs as structured semantic graphs, efficiently expressing

(a) Retrieval time with increasing repository size.

(b) LARGE parallel VMI retrieval (42 VMIs).

Figure 7: Expelliarmus scalability analysis.

the functional requirements between the base image and the different software packages. Such an approach allows clustering multiple VMIs into a single master graph that expedites similarity computation. Second, Expelliarmus enables a semantic-aware VMI decomposition and base image selection that extracts and subsequently stores non-redundant base image and software packages only. Third, Expelliarmus performs VMI assembly on-the-fly, either by fetching initially uploaded software packages or by selecting compatible and semantically similar packages already existing in the repository. We evaluated Expelliarmus over a representative set of synthetic Cloud VMIs on a real testbed. Results show that semantic-aware management of VMIs is able to reduce the repository size by 2.3 – 22 times compared to three related systems, with significant VMI publishing and slight retrieval performance improvement. Currently, Expelliarmus supports Linux VMIs, while managing Windows VMIs is part of our future work. We also plan to extend Expelliarmus to support automated containerization of VMIs with multiple container service functionalities.

Acknowledgment

This work received funding from:

- 1) European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, grant agreement 825134, “Smart Social Media Ecosystem in a Blockchain Federated Environment (ARTICONF)”;

- 2) Austrian Agency for International Cooperation in Education and Research (OeAD-GmbH) and Indian Department of Science and Technology (DST), project number, IN 20/2018, “Energy Aware Workflow Compiler for Future Heterogeneous Systems”.

Artifact description

We present in this section the reproducibility artifact of our implementation and experimental validation.

A. Release

We prototyped Expelliarmus in Python with an easy command line interface released on GitHub¹⁰.

B. Hardware dependencies

We implemented and tested Expelliarmus on an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 5218 server @ 2.30 GHz with 384 GB of DDR4 memory and 9.6 TB of SSD storage. The software, however, is portable and has no hardware dependencies.

C. Software dependencies

We tested Expelliarmus on an Ubuntu 18.04 LTS system, however, it runs on any Linux-based environment. The software dependencies include `libguestfs`, `qemu`, and `sqlite`.

D. Data sets

We created each VMI using `virt-builder`, an efficient tool to build a variety of images for local and Cloud use. The minimal script to create a VMI is listed below:

```
#!/bin/bash
# path to libguestfs
../../libguestfs-1.36.13/run virt-builder ubuntu-16.04 \
-o Image.qcow2 \
--size 4G \
--format qcow2 \
--root-password password:123 \
--edit '/etc/default/grub:/'
↵ ^GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX_DEFAULT=
↵ .* /GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX_DEFAULT= "console=tty0
↵ console=ttyS0,115200n8"/' \
--run-command update-grub \
--install "dpkg-repack,fakeroot,dpkg-dev" \
--update \
--write /etc/default/locale: "$LANG=\"en_US.UTF-8\"" \
--append /etc/default/locale: "$LANGUAGE=\"en_US\"" \
--firstboot-command 'userdel -r builder && useradd -m -p
↵ "" builder ; chage -d 0 builder'
```

We further shrank the created VMIs to remove the allocated space not used for storage. Initially, we executed following commands on the guest OS:

```
$ dd if=/dev/zero of=/mytempfile
$ rm -f /mytempfile
```

¹⁰<https://github.com/ExpelliarmusSuperComp/Expelliarmus>

Furthermore, we used the following commands to shrink the VMI disk use without compression:

```
$ mv Image.qcow2 Image.qcow2_backup
$ qemu-img convert -O qcow2 Image.qcow2_backup
↪ Image.qcow2
```

E. Expelliarmus Installation

We tested the following installation steps on Ubuntu 18.04 LTS, however, Expelliarmus can be installed on any Linux environment with manual build for libguestfs.

E.1. Requirements

1. Python version greater than 2.7;
2. Python newtorkx module;
3. libguestfs-tools module version 1.36.x or higher;
4. python-guestfs module.

E.2. Installation steps

```
$ mkdir Expelliarmus
$ cd Expelliarmus
$ git clone https://github.com/
↪ ExpelliarmusSuperComp/Expelliarmus
$ cd ../../
$ apt install libguestfs-tools
$ apt install libguestfs-dev
$ apt install python-guestfs
$ wget "download.libguestfs.org/1.36
↪ -stable/libguestfs-1.36.13.tar.gz"
$ tar -xf libguestfs-1.36.13.tar.gz
$ cd libguestfs-1.36.13
$ apt-get build-dep libguestfs
$ apt install autoconf automake libtool-bin gettext
$ ./configure
$ make
$ cd ../Expelliarmus/Expelliarmus/
$ python main.py
$ Please provide path to libguestfs:
$ Expelliarmus ready to use:
```

E.3. Troubleshooting

1. Error: "libguestfs: error: tar_in"
\$ Echo dash >/user/lib /x86_64-linux-gnu
↪ /guestfs/supermin.d /zz-dash-packages
2. Error: "suprmin exited with status 1"
\$ chmod 0644 /boot/vmlinuz*

References

- [1] Ammons, G., Bala, V., Mummert, T., Reimer, D., Zhang, X., 2011. Virtual machine images as structured data: The mirage image library, in: Proceedings of the 3rd USENIX Conference on Hot Topics in Cloud Computing, USENIX Association, Berkeley, CA, USA. pp. 22–22. URL: <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=2170444.2170466>.
- [2] Barham, P., Dragovic, B., Fraser, K., Hand, S., Harris, T., Ho, A., Neugebauer, R., Pratt, I., Warfield, A., 2003. Xen and the art of virtualization, in: Proceedings of the Nineteenth ACM Symposium on Operating Systems Principles, ACM, New York, NY, USA. pp. 164–177. URL: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/945445.945462>, doi:10.1145/945445.945462.
- [3] Beach, B., 2014. Pro PowerShell for Amazon Web Services: DevOps for the AWS Cloud. 1st ed., Apress, Berkely, CA, USA.
- [4] Broder, A.Z., 2000. Identifying and filtering near-duplicate documents, in: Proceedings of the 11th Annual Symposium on Combinatorial Pattern Matching, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg. pp. 1–10. URL: <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=647819.736184>.
- [5] Buyya, R., Yeo, C., Venugopal, S., Broberg, J., Brandic, I., 2009. Cloud computing and emerging it platforms: Vision, hype, and reality for delivering computing as the 5th utility. Future Gener. Comput. Syst. 25, 599–616. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2008.12.001>, doi:10.1016/j.future.2008.12.001.
- [6] Campello, D., Crespo, C., Verma, A., Rangaswami, R., Jayachandran, P., 2013. Coriolis: Scalable VM clustering in clouds, in: Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Autonomic Computing (ICAC 13), USENIX, San Jose, CA. pp. 101–105. URL: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/icac13/technical-sessions/presentation/campello>.
- [7] Cherry, D., 2015. Securing SQL Server, Third Edition: Protecting Your Database from Attackers. 3rd ed., Syngress Publishing.
- [8] Chieu, T.C., Mohindra, A., Karve, A.A., Segal, A., 2009. Dynamic scaling of web applications in a virtualized cloud computing environment, in: 2009 IEEE International Conference on e-Business Engineering, pp. 281–286. doi:10.1109/ICEBE.2009.45.
- [9] Constantinescu, C., Glider, J., Chambliss, D., 2011. Mixing deduplication and compression on active data sets, in: 2011 Data Compression Conference, pp. 393–402. doi:10.1109/DCC.2011.46.
- [10] Creasy, R.J., 1981. The origin of the vm/370 time-sharing system. IBM Journal of Research and Development 25, 483–490. doi:10.1147/rd.255.0483.
- [11] Dastjerdi, A.V., Buyya, R., 2016. Fog computing: Helping the internet of things realize its potential. Computer 49, 112–116. doi:10.1109/MC.2016.245.
- [12] Felter, W., Ferreira, A., Rajamony, R., Rubio, J., 2015. An updated performance comparison of virtual machines and linux containers, in: 2015 IEEE International Symposium on Performance Analysis of Systems and Software (ISPASS), pp. 171–172. doi:10.1109/ISPASS.2015.7095802.
- [13] Hunt, J.J., Vo, K.P., Tichy, W.F., 1996. An empirical study of delta algorithms, in: Proceedings of the SCM-6 Workshop on System Configuration Management, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg. pp. 49–66. URL: <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=647175.716407>.
- [14] Jaccard, P., 1912. The distribution of the flora in the alpine zone. New Phytologist 11, 37–50. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2427226?seq=3>.
- [15] Jayaram, K., Peng, C., Zhang, Z., Kim, M., Chen, H., Lei, H., 2011. An empirical analysis of similarity in virtual machine images, in: Proceedings of the Middleware 2011 Industry Track Workshop, ACM, New York, NY, USA. pp. 6:1–6:6. URL: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/2090181.2090187>, doi:10.1145/2090181.2090187.
- [16] Jin, K., Miller, E., 2009. The effectiveness of deduplication on virtual machine disk images, in: Proceedings of SYSTOR 2009: The Israeli Experimental Systems Conference, ACM, New York, NY, USA. pp. 7:1–7:12. URL: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1534530.1534540>, doi:10.1145/1534530.1534540.
- [17] Kaur, R., Chana, I., Bhattacharya, J., 2018. Data deduplication techniques for efficient cloud storage management: A systematic review. J. Supercomput. 74, 2035–2085. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-017-2210-8>, doi:10.1007/s11227-017-2210-8.
- [18] Kochut, A., Karve, A., Nicolae, B., 2015. Towards efficient on-demand vm provisioning: Study of vm runtime i/o access patterns to shared image content, in: 2015 IFIP/IEEE International Symposium on Integrated Network Management (IM), pp. 321–329. doi:10.1109/INM.2015.7140307.
- [19] Liguori, A., Hensbergen, E., 2008. Experiences with content addressable storage and virtual disks, in: Proceedings of the First Conference on I/O Virtualization, USENIX Association, Berkeley, CA, USA. pp. 5–5. URL: <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1855865.1855870>.
- [20] Lin, X., Hibler, M., Eide, E., Ricci, R., 2015. Using deduplicat-

- ing storage for efficient disk image deployment, in: TRIDENTCOM. doi:10.4108/icst.tridentcom.2015.259963.
- [21] Liu, H., He, B., Liao, X., Jin, H., . . . Towards declarative and data-centric virtual machine image management in iaas clouds. *IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing*, 1 URL: doi.ieee-computer-society.org/10.1109/TCC.2017.2728066, doi:10.1109/TCC.2017.2728066.
- [22] Liu, M., Yang, C., Jiang, Q., Chen, X., Ma, J., Ren, J., 2018. Updatable block-level deduplication with dynamic ownership management on encrypted data, in: 2018 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC), pp. 1–7. doi:10.1109/ICC.2018.8422446.
- [23] Longo, F., Ghosh, R., Naik, V.K., Trivedi, K.S., 2011. A scalable availability model for infrastructure-as-a-service cloud, in: 2011 IEEE/IFIP 41st International Conference on Dependable Systems Networks (DSN), pp. 335–346. doi:10.1109/DSN.2011.5958247.
- [24] Lu, G., Jin, Y., Du, D.H.C., 2010. Frequency based chunking for data de-duplication, in: 2010 IEEE International Symposium on Modeling, Analysis and Simulation of Computer and Telecommunication Systems, pp. 287–296. doi:10.1109/MASCOTS.2010.37.
- [25] Mandagere, N., Zhou, P., Smith, M., Uttamchandani, S., 2008. Demystifying data deduplication, in: Proceedings of the ACM/IFIP/USENIX Middleware '08 Conference Companion, ACM, New York, NY, USA. pp. 12–17. URL: http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1462735.1462739, doi:10.1145/1462735.1462739.
- [26] Meister, D., Kaiser, J., Brinkmann, A., Cortes, T., Kuhn, M., Kunkel, J., 2012. A study on data deduplication in hpc storage systems, in: Proceedings of the International Conference on High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis, IEEE Computer Society Press, Los Alamitos, CA, USA. pp. 7:1–7:11. URL: http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=2388996.2389006.
- [27] Nam, Y.J., Park, D., Du, D.H.C., 2012. Assuring demanded read performance of data deduplication storage with backup datasets, in: 2012 IEEE 20th International Symposium on Modeling, Analysis and Simulation of Computer and Telecommunication Systems, pp. 201–208. doi:10.1109/MASCOTS.2012.32.
- [28] Ng, C.H., Lee, P., 2013. Revdedup: A reverse deduplication storage system optimized for reads to latest backups, in: Proceedings of the 4th Asia-Pacific Workshop on Systems, ACM, New York, NY, USA. pp. 15:1–15:7. URL: http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/2500727.2500731, doi:10.1145/2500727.2500731.
- [29] Ng, C.H., Ma, M., Wong, T.Y., Lee, P., Lui, J., 2011. Live deduplication storage of virtual machine images in an open-source cloud, in: Proceedings of the 12th ACM/IFIP/USENIX International Conference on Middleware, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg. pp. 81–100. URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-25821-3_5, doi:10.1007/978-3-642-25821-3_5.
- [30] Nicolae, B., Kochut, A., Karve, A., 2015. Discovering and leveraging content similarity to optimize collective on-demand data access to iaas cloud storage, in: 2015 15th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing, pp. 211–220. doi:10.1109/CCGrid.2015.156.
- [31] Rabin, M., 1981. Fingerprinting by Random Polynomials. Center for Research in Computing Technology: Center for Research in Computing Technology, Center for Research in Computing Techn., Aiken Computation Laboratory, Univ. URL: https://books.google.at/books?id=Emu_tgAACAAJ.
- [32] Razavi, K., Kielmann, T., 2013. Scalable virtual machine deployment using vm image caches, in: Proceedings of the International Conference on High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis, ACM, New York, NY, USA. pp. 65:1–65:12. URL: http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/2503210.2503274, doi:10.1145/2503210.2503274.
- [33] Reimer, D., Thomas, A., Ammons, G., Mummert, T., Alpern, B., Bala, V., 2008. Opening black boxes: Using semantic information to combat virtual machine image sprawl, in: Proceedings of the Fourth ACM SIGPLAN/SIGOPS International Conference on Virtual Execution Environments, ACM, New York, NY, USA. pp. 111–120. URL: http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1346256.1346272, doi:10.1145/1346256.1346272.
- [34] Sahoo, J., Mohapatra, S., Lath, R., 2010. Virtualization: A survey on concepts, taxonomy and associated security issues, in: 2010 Second International Conference on Computer and Network Technology, pp. 222–226. doi:10.1109/ICCNT.2010.49.
- [35] Saurabh, N., Kimovski, D., Ostermann, S., Prodan, R., 2016. VM image repository and distribution models for federated clouds: State of the art, possible directions and open issues, in: Euro-Par Workshops, Springer. pp. 260–271.
- [36] Saurabh, N., Remmers, J., Kimovski, D., Prodan, R., Barbosa, J.G., 2019. Semantics-aware virtual machine image management in iaas clouds, in: 2019 IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium (IPDPS), pp. 418–427. doi:10.1109/IPDPS.2019.00052.
- [37] Schulz, G., 2011. Cloud and Virtual Data Storage Networking. Auerbach Publications, Boston, MA, USA.
- [38] Shi, W., Dustdar, S., 2016. The promise of edge computing. *Computer* 49, 78–81. doi:10.1109/MC.2016.145.
- [39] Smith, J.E., Nair, R., 2005. The architecture of virtual machines. *Computer* 38, 32–38.
- [40] Sun, C., He, L., Wang, Q., Willenborg, R., 2008. Simplifying service deployment with virtual appliances, in: 2008 IEEE International Conference on Services Computing, pp. 265–272. doi:10.1109/SCC.2008.53.
- [41] Vaquero, L.M., Rodero-Merino, L., Buyya, R., 2011. Dynamically scaling applications in the cloud. *SIGCOMM Comput. Commun. Rev.* 41, 45–52. URL: http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1925861.1925869, doi:10.1145/1925861.1925869.
- [42] Varghese, B., Buyya, R., 2017. Next generation cloud computing: New trends and research directions. *CoRR abs/1707.07452*. URL: http://arxiv.org/abs/1707.07452, arXiv:1707.07452.
- [43] Xu, J., Zhang, W., Ye, S., Wei, J., Huang, T., 2014. A lightweight virtual machine image deduplication backup approach in cloud environment, in: 2014 IEEE 38th Annual Computer Software and Applications Conference, pp. 503–508. doi:10.1109/COMPSAC.2014.73.
- [44] Xu, J., Zhang, W., Zhang, Z., Wang, T., Huang, T., 2016. Clustering-based acceleration for virtual machine image deduplication in the cloud environment. *J. Syst. Softw.* 121, 144–156. URL: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2016.02.021, doi:10.1016/j.jss.2016.02.021.
- [45] Xu, M., Zhu, Y., Lee, P.P.C., Xu, Y., 2015. Even data placement for load balance in reliable distributed deduplication storage systems, in: 2015 IEEE 23rd International Symposium on Quality of Service (IWQoS), pp. 349–358. doi:10.1109/IWQoS.2015.7404754.
- [46] Zhao, X., Zhang, Y., Wu, Y., Chen, K., Jiang, J., Li, K., 2014. Liquid: A scalable deduplication file system for virtual machine images. *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems* 25, 1257–1266. doi:10.1109/TPDS.2013.173.
- [47] Zhao, Z., Martin, P., Wang, J., Taal, A., Jones, A., Taylor, I., Stankovski, V., Vega, I.G., Suci, G., Ulisses, A., de Laat, C., 2015. Developing and operating time critical applications in clouds: The state of the art and the switch approach. *Procedia Computer Science* 68, 17 – 28. URL: http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050915030653, doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.09.220. 1st International Conference on Cloud Forward: From Distributed to Complete Computing.
- [48] Zhao, Z., Taal, A., Jones, A., Taylor, I., Stankovski, V., Vega, I.G., Hidalgo, F.J., Suci, G., Ulisses, A., Ferreira, P., de Laat, C., 2015. A software workbench for interactive, time critical and highly self-adaptive cloud applications (switch), in: 2015 15th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing, pp. 1181–1184. doi:10.1109/CCGrid.2015.73.
- [49] Zhu, B., Li, K., Patterson, H., 2008. Avoiding the disk bottleneck in the data domain deduplication file system, in: Proceedings of the 6th USENIX Conference on File and Storage Technologies, USENIX Association, Berkeley, CA, USA. pp. 18:1–18:14. URL: http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1364813.1364831.

Nishant Saurabh is a research assistant at University of Klagenfurt, Austria and pursuing his Ph.D. at University of Innsbruck, Austria since 2015. Prior to start of Ph.D., he obtained his MSc. degree specialized in High Performance Distributed Computing from

Vrije Universiteit, Netherlands; and received his B.E degree specialized in computer science and engineering from PRMITR affiliated to SGBAU University, India. His research areas include resource management and placement optimization in the field of parallel and distributed systems.

Shajulin Benedict graduated from Manonmaniam Sunderanar University, India, in 2001; received his M.E Degree in Digital Communication and Computer Networking from A.K.C.E, Anna University, India in 2004; and got his Ph.D degree in the area of Grid scheduling under Anna University,

India. He served as Professor at SXCCE Research Centre of Anna University, India. Currently, he works at the Indian Institute of Information Technology Kottayam, Kerala, India. His research interests include compilers, HPC, Cloud, Grid scheduling and performance analysis of exascale applications.

Jorge G. Barbosa received his BSc degree in Electrical and Computer Engineering from Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto (FEUP), Portugal; MSc in Digital Systems from University of Manchester Institute of Science and Technology, England, in 1993, and PhD in Electrical and Computer Engineering from FEUP, Portugal,

in 2001. Since 2001 he is an Assistant Professor at FEUP. His research interests include parallel and distributed computing, heterogeneous computing, scheduling in heterogeneous environments and cloud computing.

Radu Prodan is professor in distributed systems at the Institute of Software Technology, University of Klagenfurt. He received his PhD in 2004 from the Vienna University of Technology and was Associate Professor until 2018 at the University of Innsbruck,

Austria. His research interests include performance, optimisation, and resource management tools for parallel and distributed applications. He authored over 100 publications and received two IEEE best paper awards.